

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 – GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D2.4.1 “New data about sustainable production of new materials from biomasses”

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M8 to M 24
Periodic report date and version:	Ver1 30-07-2025
Deliverable D2.4.1 Responsible	Arlorio
RM2 Responsible	Arlorio

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	Delivery Date (actual)
<i>[number]</i>	<i>[name]</i>	<i>[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]</i>	<i>[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]</i>	<i>[month number]</i>	<i>[dd/mm/yyyy]</i>
D2.1	Data about chemical and nutritional profiling of raw wastes and by products	R	PU	M14	18/04/2024
D2.2.1	On-line lab-scale technical multi-device for waste processing*	Other (material)	PU	M18	25/10/2024
D2.2.2	Delivery of protocols (lab-scale) ready to scale-up the production of new high-value material (in collaboration with Companies)	R	PU	M22	16/02/2025
D2.3.1	New data about valorized matrices characterization and high value products	R	PU	M28	30/09/2025
D2.3.2	New characterized ingredients/materials for food, nutraceuticals, pharma and cosmetic applications	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.4.1	New data about sustainable production of new materials from biomasses	R	PU	M24	24/12/2025
D2.4.2	New characterized materials from biomasses	Other (material) (& Report)	PU	M30	29/09/2025
D2.5.2	Porous sorbents from biomasses valorization	Other (material) (& Report)	PU	M30	29/09/2025
D2.6.1	New material produced at pilot scale ready to the formulation or co-formulation (in collaboration with Companies)	Other (material) (& Report)	PU	M32	30/09/2025
D2.6.2	New well characterized process and formulated pilot-products (in collaboration with Companies)	R/Other (Material)	PU	M32	24/12/2025

D2.7	Report on the adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	R	PU	M32	29/09/2025
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A) INTRODUCTION

The work and the outcomes reported in this Deliverable are related to the activity scheduled in Task 2.2 (focusing on Sub-Task 2.2.2) and Task 2.3. The main goal was the identification and evaluation of the real impact of the processing selected for the pilot production of new ingredients/food materials.

Even if LCA was integral part of the activity in this part of the Project, some problems related to the recovery of data (particularly concerning the scale up in collaboration with Companies) was delayed, and in some case not available for confidentiality in order to complete this task. Anyway, a mitigation activity by RM6 (Industrial symbiosis) was done in another matrix, substituting the evaluation scheduled in Task 2.3. Moreover, additional activity related to the set-up and development of new combined processes was conducted by the partners, particularly concerning cocoa hulls and rice husks, in order to substitute lack of the LCA analysis.

B) ROLE OF PARTNERS

The role of the Partners involved in this activity (principally UPO, PoliTO, Envipark) was to focused on the selection of the best performing protocols and process to up-cycle the raw biomasses in order to obtain their complete characterization and definition, particularly evaluating i) energetic parameters, ii) overall process cost, iii) impact on the environment and iv) sustainability. More data and work is required in order to complete a real LCA analysis of these process, as anticipated.

C) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

The activities reported in Deliverable D2.4.1 focus on the selection and evaluation of sustainable processing routes for the production of new materials and ingredients from biomass residues. The work addresses energetic performance, environmental sustainability, and potential scalability of the selected technologies, in line with the objectives of Task 2.2 and Task 2.3 of the GRIP Flagship Project.

- ***Enzyme-driven processes***

Enzyme-assisted processes were identified as particularly promising from a sustainability perspective. These technologies typically operate under mild temperature and pressure conditions, resulting in relatively low direct energy consumption compared to conventional

thermal or chemical treatments. In addition, enzymatic selectivity reduces the generation of by-products and simplifies downstream purification, with positive implications for overall environmental performance.

However, the life-cycle sustainability of enzyme-based processes is strongly influenced by enzyme production, stability, and reusability (particularly concerning the enzymes immobilization). High enzyme dosages (or single-use applications) may partially offset the energetic advantages observed at the process level.

Enzymatic treatments of cocoa bean shells have been investigated to improve their fermentability and functional properties, demonstrating the feasibility of mild bioprocessing routes for this side stream (Disca et al., 2024). These approaches are consistent with low-energy, food-grade valorization strategies.

Regarding the scale-up of the process, more data are required particularly regarding the availability of bulk-level enzymes, able to reduce the cost considered at laboratory level.

- *Hydrothermal processes*

Hydrothermal technologies, including i) steam explosion process and ii) subcritical water extractions/ treatments, were applied to lignocellulosic-rich residues such as cocoa shells and rice husks. These processes rely primarily on water as the processing medium and avoid or minimize the use of organic solvents, aligning well with green chemistry principles. From an energetic standpoint, hydrothermal processes are more energy-intensive than enzymatic treatments, due to elevated temperatures and pressures required. Nevertheless, their sustainability profile can be significantly improved through short residence times and heat recovery strategies, particularly when implemented at pilot or industrial scale. Anyway, the relative high cost of these processes is well balanced by the low-impact at level of environmental contamination, as well as by the reduction of the costs related to the use of organic solvents.

As described in many Deliverables of RM2-GRIP, the cocoa bean shells are recognized as a valuable source of dietary fiber and bioactive compounds and they have been successfully processed using green extraction and hydrothermal approaches (Sánchez et al., 2023; Belwal et al., 2022). Subcritical water extraction, in particular, enables the recovery of functional fractions while avoiding hazardous solvents, although optimization is required to balance extraction efficiency and thermal energy demand.

Also rice husks have been extensively studied as a lignocellulosic residue suitable for hydrothermal processing. Subcritical water hydrolysis has been shown to effectively modify rice husk structure and generate hydrolyzed fractions with added value (Draszewski et al., 2022). Furthermore, integrated strategies combining steam explosion with subsequent enzymatic hydrolysis have demonstrated improved sugar yields from rice husks, highlighting the potential benefits of combined hydrothermal–biological approaches (Draszewski et al., 2025).

The overall outcomes of the RM2 activity related to the development of the final scaled products (as described also in the Final Report), confirm that the application of these processes is useful and performing to produce new up-cycled ingredients/materials, allowing to identify and set-up new single and combined process for the valorization of the raw materials.

- *Ultrasound-assisted processes*

Ultrasound-assisted processing was evaluated as a process ensuring the extraction intensification strategy. Ultrasound can enhance mass transfer, reduce processing times, and lower solvent consumption, potentially reducing overall energy use when applied as a pre-treatment or in combination with other technologies. The electrical energy demand of ultrasound systems is highly dependent on operating conditions, emphasizing the need for careful optimization to ensure net sustainability benefits.

- Combined processes and LCA considerations

As highlighted in the deliverable draft, the combination of multiple technologies (e.g., hydrothermal treatments coupled with enzymatic or ultrasound-assisted steps) increases the complexity of LCA due to data availability and scale-related uncertainties.

The use of pilot-scale equipment not yet standardized at commercial level further complicates comparative assessments. Nonetheless, the results obtained indicate that integrated, well-optimized process chains represent a promising pathway for the sustainable valorization of biomass residues within a circular economy framework.

Regarding the material considered in this study (particularly concerning cocoa-derived products and cocoa-by products) a very limited amount of data are available in scientific literature. Moreover, an overall four phases LCA approach (ICONTEC, 2007) as following described could be applied in the next future, in order to evaluate if the process which

allowed to obtain at pre-competitive level the final formulated products described in the Final Report is “sustainable” at global level.

- The first step consists in establish the goal and scope definition, which provides the outline and guidance for the study: this step was achieved in the RM2 study, particularly regarding the production of high value products from cocoa bean shells useful to produce food supplements with antioxidant properties;
- the second step is the “inventory analysis”, where the consumption of resources and generation of emissions, wastes and energy for the analyzed system are estimated; this phase identifies the inventory flows and quantifies them, based on multiple data sources. The completing of this step was not achieved at this step of the project, principally because some data were not disclosed by the Companies involved in the processing collaboration with UPO.
- In the third phase, the Life Cycle Impacts Assessment (LCIA) must be carried out; LCIA aims to evaluate the magnitude and significance of the potential environmental impacts associated with impact categories and category indicators. Also this step was partially achieved.

Finally, in the interpretation phase the results of the two previous phases are evaluated according to the defined goal and scope to get the respective conclusions and recommendations.

A good example of application of the LCA approach was recently made by Tovar et al. (2024), on cocoa pod husk, demonstrating that across all transformation processes, electricity consumption during the transformation process emerged as the primary contributor to the LCA results. Unfortunately, no specific data about LCA on cocoa bean shells were published to date, and any kind of “reference” conventional process for the comparison is available, complicating the evaluation.

Finally, we highlight that this accessory activity didn't lead to significant problems related to the scale up of the process and the pilot production of the final products selected, produced and completely characterized under the chemical and nutritional point of view.

References

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